

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

E-office implementation to support office administration activities

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Abstract

Office Administration is a science that deals with planning, organising, implementing, and controlling all matters relating to the life cycle of business and business information in the company. And very closely related to correspondence or correspondence, archives, and communication skills. With the existence of e-office, it can manage and integrate computer-based such as digital archives, or correspondence that does not require physical letters or paperless. Therefore, due to the development of technological disruption, the purpose of this research is how to build a system and application of e-office for office administration and find out the advantages of implementing e-office. This research uses the literature study method by reviewing books, journals, and related research.

Keywords: E-office; Office Administration; Economy; Technology Disruption; Office work.

1. Introduction

Office Administration is not only a science but also an activity that cannot be separated from an organisation by managing data and information to achieve organisational or company goals systematically. So the existence of e-office is crucial because of the demands of the times and all companies from various business lines have integrated their services with computerisation. The need for e-office is to facilitate the task of someone whose work is related to office administration such as correspondence, archives, and public relations. The demands of the times in addition to increasing the competence level of its workers also understand the changes in computer-based technology. Because there are several organisations that still use manual methods in their organisational activities.

Office administration seen from the meaning of its activities is the science related to planning, organising, implementing, and controlling all matters relating to business data and information in the company and when viewed from the meaning of science is knowledge, skills, and attitudes in completing organisational work, assisting and handling the work and tasks of the leadership as well as the demands of its work is to study the knowledge and skills of correspondence, archive management, office management, office automation, and others.

Electronic Office or E-Office is a system that is closely related to administration by centring the elements of an organisation where data, information and communication are made through telecommunications media. E-Office exists to increase the need for the use and processing of information technology-based data for office work.

information technology-based data processing for office work with the development of this era of technological disruption, the use of computers is a tool for processing data into information electronically.

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2. Methods

This research uses a literature study method by reviewing books, journals and related research that discusses electronic office or e-office. The results of these various reviews are used to identify the implementation of e-office in office administration activities.

3. Discussion and results

Office work is usually considered as basic work that does not require the role of technology in it. However, with the growing role of information, everything related to office administration must be technologically responsive because of the wider services that must be provided in office management activities to manage organisational information in an actual and comprehensive manner.

Information management is needed by every formal organisation to produce goods or services with the aim of knowing whether the company makes a profit or not. So it can be said that information in the company is described as the brain in the human body, so it must be collected, processed, processed, and communicated through tools or systems that apply in every company.

Decision making should be taken from accurate information. So good or bad information can be reviewed through the data or information received because it can affect the quality of decisions that will be made by managers.

Obtained from the results of the literature review analysis is that it has similarities, namely the distribution of incoming and outgoing mail easily to internal company or external parties, storing archives using an online database as a form of paperless or reducing the use of paper, helping employees in displaying and monitoring information received from superiors.

So in the process of designing the system what is needed is complaints, solutions, the impact of manual solutions, solutions with e-office, and the impact of solutions with ie-office. Because from this data will form a concept that is made and can be adjusted based on the requests that have been poured. Because to make e-office run smoothly is to adjust to the needs of the company, and there are applications that can be used in general or can be purchased through third parties, and applications that are specifically designed for the company so as not to be hacked by other parties.

After making the concept, the next step is to design the system with a prototype that is tested by several divisions, and from the trial, it can distribute forms in online form such as google form so that the distribution of suggestions related to evaluation can be received directly to the division concerned. And after receiving suggestions and criticisms, the prototype application is updated and can become a finished product that is easy to use and useful.

One does not have to conduct meetings in the form of presence in the room but can be by teleconference, can be with intermediaries such as the Zoom application, Google Meet, Teams and others.

4. Conclusion

It can be concluded that the implementation of e-office on office administration activities can have a positive impact on its application, namely speeding up time and minimising energy, reducing the use of paper and other stationery, archives are stored in an online database to facilitate their search and anticipate file loss, making it easier for someone to conduct meetings in the form of teleconferences to minimise travel costs and time, and facilitate the process of receiving, distributing, and monitoring data and information provided both ongoing and completed and in designing an e-office application must be adjusted to the company's line of business to get good results as well, because it can produce useful data and information as a basis for considering policy decisions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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